

Medical Negligence In India: A Judicial Approach

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Abstract The concept of medical negligence has undergone a major transformation from being a crime to a tort. Medical negligence means negligence on the part of the doctor to act in accordance with medical standards in vogue, being practiced by an ordinarily reasonably competent man practicing the same art. It suggests some irregular conduct on the part of any member of the medical profession or related services in discharge of his/her professional duties. The civil law of medical negligence as developed by the Courts is very different from the criminal law since while the former primarily strives to provide compensation to the patients or to their relatives, the latter concentrates more on punishing the negligent medical practitioner. Under civil law, liability arises for the tort of negligence as applied to medical accidents and the development of the concept of 'duty of care' in negligence as a whole has a constant bearing on 'duty of care' in the medical context .

Keywords Negligence, Tort, Criminal law, Compensation, Liability.

Introduction Criminal negligence same as culpable neglect or failure to exercise that reasonable care and precaution to guard against injury, the public generally and to an individual in particular. It is not merely lack of necessary care, attention and skill. Gross lack of competence or wanton indifference to his patient's safety (arising from such disregard for the patient's whole life and safety such that the matter goes beyond compensation between subjects) is necessary to hold the person liable for criminal medical negligence.

Objective of study The objective of this study is to judicial approach of medical negligence in India.

Review of Literature **Tapas Kumar Koley** has covered the wide range of issues including the duties, responsibilities, and rights of doctors; likely areas of litigation in medical specialties consent of patients; and compensation. **Anoop K. Kaushal** its focus on discussing a large number of diseases and the prevailing protocols of clinical practices followed in treatment and discussed before the courts. He has discussed distinctly, too many decisions of the courts on cases of medical negligence. Jagdish Singh and Vishwa Bhushan have analysed on various cases decided by the Supreme Court, High Courts, National and State Consumer Commissions and arranged specialty-wise. The important foreign cases also given in digest form stating therein particular negligence which occurred and the compensation awarded.

Main Text

Negligence per se Deliberating on the absence of basic qualifications of a homeopathic doctor to practice allopathy in Poonam Verma vs. Ashwin Patel and Ors. (1996) 4 SCC 322, the Supreme Court held that a person who does not have knowledge of a particular system of medicine but practices in that system is a quack. Where a person is guilty of negligence per se, no further proof is needed.

Duty on the part of a hospital and doctor to obtain prior consent of a patient

There exists a duty to obtain prior consent (with respect to living patients) for the purpose of diagnosis, treatment, organ transplant, research purposes, disclosure of medical records, and teaching and medico-legal purposes. With respect to the dead in regard to pathological post mortem, medico-legal post mortem, organ transplant (for legal heirs), and for disclosure of medical record, it is important that informed consent of the patient is obtained. Consent can be given in the following ways:

Express Consent: It may be oral or in writing. Both these categories of consents are of equal value, written consent can be considered as superior because of its evidential value.

Implied Consent: Implied consent may be implied by patient's conduct.

Tacit Consent: Tacit consent means implied consent understood without being stated.

Surrogate consent: This consent is given by family members. Generally, courts have held that consent of family members with the written approval of 2 physicians sufficiently protects a patient's interest.

Advance consent, proxy consent, and presumed consent are also used. While the term advance consent is the consent given by patient in advance, proxy consent indicates consent given by an authorized person. As mentioned earlier, informed consent obtained after explaining all possible risks and side effects is superior to all other forms of consent.

The government hospitals run by the state are bound by duty to extend medical assistance for preserving human life. Failure on the part of a government hospital to provide timely medical treatment to a person in need of such treatment results in the infringement of his right to life guaranteed under Art. 21.

304 A or Section 336/337/338 of the Indian Penal Code, 1860 (IPC) alleging rashness or negligence on the part of the doctors resulting in loss of life or injury of varying degree to the patient. This has given rise to a situation of great distrust from unnecessary and arbitrary complaints, is the need of the hour.

Types of Medical Negligence

1. Misdiagnosis

Misdiagnosis occurs when a medical professional fails to diagnose what condition a patient is suffering from. This may be because they think the patient has a different illness, or because they do not notice their condition at all.

2. Surgical Negligence

Surgery almost always comes with some inherent risk, but sometimes mistakes are made that should never happen. These 'never events' include foreign objects being left in patients or the wrong area of the body being operated on.

3. Anaesthesia

It is a common part of medical treatment and something most of us are given at some point in our lives, whether it be in the hospital or at the dentist.

4. Prescription and Medication Errors

Thousands of prescriptions are written and dispensed each day, and in rare cases, errors can occur. These mistakes may take the form of the wrong medication or dosage being given to you, medications being prescribed together that should not be, or medications being given to patients despite knowing they are allergic to them.

5. Long-Term Negligent Treatment

Most medical conditions are not cured overnight. Instead, it is likely that a patient will need long-term treatment or care. Where a medical professional fails to monitor the impact of the treatment properly or does not schedule the correct follow-up appointment, medical negligence can take place.

6. Negligent Medical Advice

While most of us rely on a medical professional's expertise for treatment, patients are still meant to be advised on any risks, side effects or alternatives available. This advice

is integral to being able to make an informed decision.

7. Pregnancy and Birth Injuries

Birth Injuries can include any harm the mother or baby suffers either during and after the pregnancy. These injuries can have life-changing ramifications for both mother and child, and examples include cerebral palsy, bowel trauma and maternal diabetes.

8. Dental Negligence

It is important to note that it is not just your local NHS doctor who can provide negligent care. A number of medical negligence claims come about as a result of low-quality treatment from a dentist.

9. Negligent Cosmetic Care

Cosmetic surgery is becoming more and more popular among both men and women. So, it is no surprise that we are seeing a rise in the number of medical negligence cases resulting from cosmetic surgery.

Important Case Laws Related to Medical Negligence

An appellant doctor was found by the State Commission to be responsible for leaving ribbon gauze in the right side of the nose after a septoplasty resulting in several complications. The complainant suffered and had to be under treatment all the while the National Commission confirmed the order and observed that it has no option but to deduce that it was a clear case of medical negligence on the part of the appellant. The National Commission in the case of Dr. Ravishankar vs. Jery K. Thomas and Anr, II (2006) CPJ 138 (NC) held that based on the facts and circumstances, the obvious deduction is that the appellant doctor is responsible for leaving behind ribbon gauze resulting in complications. Medical negligence was proved.

In the case of Pravat Kumar Mukherjee vs. Ruby General Hospital and Ors, II(2005)CPJ35(NC), the National Commission delivered a landmark decision concerning treatment of an accident victim by the hospital.

Spring Meadows Hospital v. Harjot Ahluwalia

In this case Court, held that when a young child was carried to a private hospital by parents and treated by the doctors. Then not only just the child but his parents are also treated as a consumer under the Consumer Protection Act. Hence, a parent can claim the Compensation under the Consumer Protection Act. Therefore, the court ruled in favor of the child's parents and the child who was the service's beneficiary. The hospital argued that adequate care had indeed been taken and hence would not be authorized to pay compensation for the mental agony the parents have went through. They disputed that the parents would not come under the definition of consumer in the consumer protection act. The court accurately pointed out that this contention was false since the consumer's definition under the act includes parents.

Indian Medical Association v. V.P. Shantha

The supreme court has reiterated that services rendered to a patient by a medical practitioner (except where the doctor cause services free of charge to every patient or under a contract of personal service) by way of consultation, treatment and diagnosis, both surgical and medical, would fall within the service as defined in section 2(1) (o) of the Consumer Protection Act 1986. The judgment has faced a lot of opposition from the people involved in the medical field. However, this judgment has come as a wave of relief for all the consumers. With rampant increase in commercialization of services, including medical services, the patient has now become a mere consumer. This causes deterioration in the fiduciary relationship between a doctor and his/her patient. This judgment that reaches the arms of the Consumer Protection Act, 1986 to the medical profession will undoubtedly enable to keep a check on the doctors to discharge their duties diligently, for it is always the patient's life at stake. It will make the method of treatment and surgery more transparent. One negative aspect of this judgment is that it does not prescribe any relief or Compensation for free medical services.

In **Jacob Mathew** this Court dealt with the liability of a medical practitioner in criminal law. Of course, the decision also discussed in detail the law of medical negligence in

general and indicated the parameters of fixing liability. The distinction between the concept of negligence in civil law and negligence in criminal law was highlighted. The present case deals with the law of negligence in tort. The basis of liability of a professional in tort is negligence. Unless that negligence is established, the primary liability cannot be fastened on the medical practitioner. Unless the primary liability is established, vicarious liability on the State cannot be imposed. Both in criminal jurisprudence and in civil jurisprudence, doctors are liable for consequences of negligence. In Jacob Mathew even while dealing with criminal negligence, this Court has indicated the caution needed in approaching a case of medical negligence having regard to the complexity of the human body which is subjected to treatment and the uncertainty involved in medical procedures. A doctor, in essence, needs to be inventive and has to take snap decisions especially in the course of performing surgery when some unexpected problems crop up or complication sets in. If the medical profession, as a whole, is hemmed in by threat of action, criminal and civil, the consequence will be loss to the patients. No doctor would take a risk, a justifiable risk in the circumstances of a given case, and try to save his patient from a complicated disease or in the face of an unexpected problem that confronts him during the treatment or the surgery. It is in this background that this Court has cautioned that the setting in motion of the criminal law against the medical profession should be done cautiously and on the basis of reasonably sure grounds. In criminal prosecutions or claims in tort, the burden always rests with the prosecution or the claimant. No doubt, in a given case, a doctor may be obliged to explain his conduct depending on the evidence adduced by the prosecution or by the claimant. That position does not change merely because of the caution advocated in Jacob Mathew in fixing liability for negligence, on doctors.

Conclusion

The Supreme Court may have tried to balance the scales of necessary protection and license to kill, the question we should ask ourselves is, should the concept of negligence per se be applied to proper or not. The idea of being a professional is one has the necessary qualifications and expertise and if we keep tagging every minor problem of a doctor as a negligent act for which he has to pay damages, it will take away from his freedom to act and treat his patients in the way he thinks best. Moreover, in every profession, especially medicine, there is always a certain amount of uncertainty involved and it would not be correct to allege negligence especially when it involves such a complex thing as the human body. Also, a large part of the success of the doctor depends on the co-operation of the client and this gives rise to the issue of whether one can even judge the action of the doctor based on this. Not only that, this may also give rise to frivolous litigation where if the bar for civil liability is just that of an average doctor, then someone who may want to take revenge in the profession itself may testify against the implicate causing him trouble and harassment. All these point towards not making negligence a wrongful act.

Therefore, we should be able to arrive at a situation where we can balance out both civil and criminal liability in medical negligence such that the black sheep that have entered the profession can be isolated effectively without affecting those who work in honest faith. It should neither be a license to kill nor should it be extra immunity but a via media for proper regulation.

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